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Taxonomy of member state legal requirements applicable to cross-border exchange of health and genetic data in the European 1+MG Project

Un homme qui voyage dans ce pays change de loi presque autant de fois qu'il change de chevaux de poste.

A man travelling in this country changes laws almost as often as he changes horses.

Ein Mann, der durch dieses Land reist, wechselt das Recht fast genauso oft wie die Pferde.

- Voltaire

The 1+MG aims to develop an ethical and legal governance framework to enable cross-border access to genomic and related health data for healthcare, research, and policy-making purposes. The ethical and legal governance framework must ensure compliance with both European Laws - namely the *General Data Protection Regulation* (GDPR), as well as the laws of signatory Member States. This document aims to describe the range of divergence between Member State laws relevant to the activities of the 1+MG. The scope of this document are authoritative rules with legally binding force found in statutes or regulations issued by a government agency. The taxonomy is organized according to stages in the data lifecycle - collection, generation, primary use, storage, secondary use, and results. At each stage of the life cycle, the taxonomy sections are broken down further into relevant subject matter areas potentially subject to Member State legal requirements. Within each subject matter area, Member State rules are organized into categories and compared based on their function, i.e., their effect on relevant 1+MG activities. In assessing function, one can consider common factual use cases of cross-border access to genomic and related health data for healthcare, research, and policy-making purposes (see e.g., the 1+MG Healthcare Use Case Workshop Summary). Where Member State rules are functionally equivalent, they are grouped together into the same category. This functional comparison is neutral to the formal nature of the legal rule (the regulatory field in which it applies or its scope of application). Examples are sometimes provided to provide additional context. In summary, each section provides a taxonomy describing the range of divergence between types of Member State laws.

This taxonomy focuses only on legal requirements of a public-order nature, as the most important and non-negotiable rules that have to be respected by the 1+MG. It will not look at non-binding rules found in guidelines, or at rules emanating from private-ordering such as institutional policies or contracts (which are to some degree negotiable). The taxonomy is neutral as to the source or form of the rule (e.g., criminal law; human tissue law; national data protection law; sector-specific data protection law; law implementing national data centre; binding code of conduct; common law). For example, while 1+MG is not concerned with human biosamples per se, human tissue rules may indirectly limit what data types can be made available to 1+MG. Establishing such a taxonomy of legal rules does face considerable complexity and limitations. For example, the taxonomy must presumably not only cover different Member States but also different scopes of application of those laws. Data may be collected and generated as part of healthcare provision, research projects, or national genomic initiatives (which themselves may have more of a clinical or research focus). Different rules may apply depending on the sector (e.g., public v.s. private healthcare providers). Rules may differ depending on the data type (e.g., special rules for health and/or genetic data). Rules may also differ depending on the secondary use made of the data (e.g., research, healthcare, policy-making). Some rules may be mandatory, while others may allow exceptions under certain circumstances. Also, a thematic list may not reflect the interdependencies between rules (such as the relationship between legal basis, data subject rights and technical and organizational measures).

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This taxonomy can inform the development of an ethical and legal governance framework for the 1+MG that facilitates legal compliance and legal interoperability. Legal interoperability here refers to the ability to meaningfully exchange data between countries despite certain differences between their laws. This may be achieved in various ways. The 1+MG could establish standards that respect the most restrictive national approach, among those countries which participate in the initiative. Different data could be made available in different access tiers, with each tier subject to different rules around access and use. The 1+MG could establish minimum standards (e.g., for data availability) meaning that data that cannot be meaningfully integrated and made available would be excluded from 1+MG. The taxonomy could also inform the federated architecture of the 1+MG. Federation means the data remains hosted nationally in part to reduce overlap and conflict between applicable laws. Users can still interact with the 1+MG as a single virtual cohort. Where there is no legal interoperability solution, the 1+MG may be hampered in achieving its aims, and will rely on efforts by the Member States to promote greater legal harmonization (e.g., establishing a Directive, or encouraging national legislators to voluntarily update their laws to improve further pan-European alignment).

Stage of the Data Lifecycle / Subject Matter of Regulation

- 1. Global Data Processing /** Limitations for particular groups
- 2. Global Data Processing /** Legal basis to collect or process personal data under Art. 6 GDPR and legal legitimation (i.e., exception to general prohibition) to collect/process special categories of data under Art. 9(2) GDPR
- 3. Global Data Processing /** Transparency = Information requirements beyond GDPR Art. 13
- 4. Data Collection /** Special consent requirements when collecting data directly from the data subject
- 5. Data Collection /** Special requirements when processing already existing data, where consent is absent or insufficient
- 6. Data Generation /** Data (and Metadata) Quality Requirements
- 7. Data Generation /** Data formats, ontologies, interoperability requirements
- 8. Data Subject Rights**
- 9. Storage /** Retention period
- 10. Storage /** Requirements re: pseudonymisation, de-pseudonymization
- 11. Linkage /** Requirements when processing national IDs
- 12. Hosting /** Rules for data repositories or national data centres
- 13. Secondary use /**
 - a. Permitted purposes
 - b. Legal Basis / Legitimation
 - c. Conditions
 - d. Rules applying to data users
- 14. Dissemination of Results**
- 15. TOMs (technical & organisational measures)**

Stage of the Data Lifecycle / Subject Matter of Regulation	Taxonomy of Legal Approaches (Personal Health and/or Genetic Data)	Notes
<p>1. Global Data Processing (Including Data Collection) / Limitations for particular groups</p>	<p><i>This domain explores types of legal rules that fundamentally prohibit or limit data collection from particular groups. Another way to think about this category is when is it legally possible (or not) to collect data and sequence particular groups. These particular groups may include minors (of different ages), adults with diminished capacity, vulnerable people or groups, embryos pre-implantation; embryonic tissue, fetuses, and or deceased persons. This includes global prohibitions on data processing that would also effectively impact the data collection stage.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General prohibition on collection - Collection only permitted for limited purposes - Prohibition on collection with exceptional conditions (e.g., collection for research purposes only if the research would be impossible in non-vulnerable groups, and direct benefit to the individual or age/disease group); - Collection from vulnerable groups permitted with appropriate consent, such as consent from a legally authorized representative(s)' combined with the individual's assent. There may be an additional requirement to obtain consent from the individual as soon as this is possible (e.g., minors becoming adults; adults regaining capacity). <i>See additional information in the "Consent" section below.</i> 	<p>Relevance: Ultimately states can have different fundamental limitations on what types of individuals or groups may undergo sequencing in the first place. These limitations will mean that those States cannot share such data because they simply do not exist in the first place. Differences may affect the scientific and healthcare value of cross-border access for certain purposes, as there would be a lack of comparable data. This would mean that certain groups receive less benefit from the 1+MG while others contribute more.</p>
<p>2. Global Data Processing (Including Data Collection) / Legal basis to collect/process personal data under Art. 6 GDPR and legal legitimation (i.e., exception to general prohibition) to collect/process special</p>	<p><i>This domain focuses on the legal basis for processing personal data as well as the legal legitimation for exceptionally processing some special categories of data (namely health and genetic data). This section specifically considers the legal basis/legitimation for processing data for PRIMARY purpose of providing healthcare (column A), or for conducting scientific research (column B). A separate section below (see box 11) will address the question of legal basis/legitimation concerning further processing of data for research or healthcare purposes (sometimes referred to as "secondary" or "retrospective" use).</i></p> <p><i>This section provides a list of legal bases permitted in different Member States, as well as a list of legitimations. Note that a combination of an Art 6 legal basis and an Art 9(2) legitimation will be needed in the contexts of processing whole genome sequence data and associated health data.</i></p>	<p>Relevance: available legal bases may constrain the scope of permitted further processing for e.g. research purposes. Different legal bases may lead to problems when trying to integrate data with different legal bases. There may also be conflicts for cross-border sharing with repositories or data users: what are their legal basis? Also, different legal bases may lead to different required TOM</p>

<p>categories of data under Art. 9(2) GDPR</p>	<p><i>The findings in this section are largely based on the findings of the NIVEL Report, 2020, which reported on what legal basis or bases can be relied upon in different Member States. The order of legal bases is listed according to the likelihood of use (see NIVEL Report).</i></p> <p><i>It should be considered that Member States may provide various menus of options from the list of legal bases below, e.g., only one basis available; hierarchy of legal bases; flexible choice from among multiple available bases; different basis or bases available depending on the type of data or context (e.g., public vs. private providers/nature of medical intervention).</i></p>		<p>safeguards + data subject rights (e.g., withdrawal) (see below)</p>
	<p>A. Healthcare: Legal basis/legitimation for primary healthcare purposes.</p> <p>Art 6(1): (c) Compliance with legal obligation (to record patient interactions) (e) public interest (a) Consent basis (b) Performance of a contract (<i>perhaps only for private healthcare services</i>) (f) Legitimate Interest</p> <p>Art 9(2): (h) Prevention, diagnosis, treatment (e.g., FR; NL Art 29 genetic data – for others than the data subject where significant medical interest prevails) (a) Explicit consent (g) Public interest (e.g., NL Art 28 genetic data if “in relation to the data subject”) (i) Public interest in public health</p> <p>Examples of Combinations: 6(1)(a) Consent and 9(2)(a) Consent 6(1)(c) Legal obligation + 9(2)(i) public interest in the area of public health</p>	<p>B. Research: Legal basis/legitimation for the primary purpose of conducting research. It is presumed here that the research is “genuine” research.</p> <p>Art 6(1): (a) Consent basis (e) Public Interest (f) Legitimate Interest</p> <p>Art 9(2): (a) Explicit consent (g) Substantial public interest (on the basis of law) (h) Prevention, diagnosis, treatment (i) Public interest in public health (j) Scientific research in accordance with Art 89(1)</p> <p>Available options: - Explicit consent only INCLUDING for further processing e.g Poland? - Explicit consent as default basis. Exceptions where o data is necessary + public/common interest + consent is impossible, infeasible, disproportionate effort +</p>	

	<p>6(1)(c) legal obligation + 9(2)(h) provision of health or social care 6(1)(e) public interest + 9(2)(h) provision of health or social care 6(1)(e) public interest + 9(2)(i) public interest in the field of public health 6(1)(f) legitimate interest + 9(2)(h) provision of health or social care 6(1)(c) legal obligation + 9(2)(g) public interest 6(1)(e) public interest + 9(2)(g) public interest 6(1)(b) performance of a contract + 9(2)(h) provision of health or social care Other</p>	<p>adverse effect unlikely / data subject not disproportionately harmed (UK,NL) + safeguards. (i.e. a weighing exercise) [NL]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Certain safeguards in place (e.g. pseudonymisation = AT) ○ Certain type of research (UK) ○ Certain actors (e.g. AT: public interest basis provided by law) ○ Exceptions can be exercised with / without approval of a defined board <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of Art. 9(2)(j) in national laws - No hierarchy 	
<p>3. Data Collection / Special consent requirements when collecting data directly from the data subject</p>	<p><i>This section looks at special consent requirements imposed by member state law that go beyond any requirements of the GDPR. Of particular interest are special consent requirements that apply specifically to genetic testing or genetic research. Here the focus is on requirements concerning formalities, the structure of the consent, or the process of how consent is to be obtained. Content or informational requirements are addressed separately as part of the “transparency” section.</i></p> <p><i>This section does not exclusively address a single legal basis. The previous section addresses differences between Member States regarding what legal bases are available (or restricted). Where the art 6 legal basis / article 9 legitimation is consent, member states may impose additional requirements or specifics on what qualifies as freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous, and explicit consent. Where another legal basis is used such as 6(1)e/9(2)j, Member States may still apply special consent requirements, e.g., as a safeguard for certain types of processing. For consent relating to the return of individual findings of health relevance, see Results section below.</i></p> <p><i>Note, where (explicit) consent is the legal basis, the GDPR outlines conditions in articles 4(11), 6(1)(a), 7, and 9(2)(a), e.g., that consent be “freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous”, withdrawable at any time, clearly distinguishable from other matters, and “in an intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language”.</i></p>	<p>Relevance : strict consent requirements relevant if applicable to further processing may restrict data availability; 1+MG may share accountability for ensuring local consent requirements are respected.</p>	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explicit consent required (e.g., to genetic testing including specific elements / statements to be covered; HU) - Consent (as a safeguard where explicit consent is not the legal basis/legitimation) (FR) - Written consent (e.g. specifically for genetic testing; research with special category data) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o exception allowing to just document consent if the modalities of the investigation make it particularly burdensome to to acquire it in writing (IT) - Genetic counselling prior to consent (e.g., predictive genetic testing) - Implied consent (e.g., for primary healthcare processing) - Opt-out consent (e.g., for further processing of healthcare data for research purposes) - Consent must be specific to the research project (i.e., broad consent not permitted) (e.g., for all special category data; for genetic data; for genetic data with high chance of incidental findings). - For minors, requirement to seek consent from the individual when he/she reaches a certain age (e.g., 15/18) (<i>See also "Transparency"</i>) 	
<p>4. Data Collection / Special requirements when processing data, where consent is absent or insufficient</p>	<p><i>This section considers special requirements needed to process data where consent is absent or insufficient. The legal basis/legitimation cannot therefore be (explicit) consent. Under other legal bases, Member States may provide two distinct pathways: 1) use where some form of consent is required (consent as a safeguard), and 2) alternative pathways subject to authorization and/or certain conditions. Under this second pathway, the authorizations and conditions described may only apply in certain contexts, depending on the type of data, user context (e.g., public vs. private providers/nature of medical intervention), or type of processing (re-use for health research; disclosure to a third party, international transfer).</i></p> <p>Entity providing authorisation to process personal data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No exceptional authorisation possible. - Data Protection Authority - authorization for specific purposes (e.g., research project (IT)). - Data Protection Authority - authorization for general purposes (e.g., research by specific categories of processing and controller with certain measures in place (IT)). - Specialized national committee (e.g., Irish HRCDC) - Research Ethics Committee (REC) - Director of institution - Data Access Committee (legally appointed - e.g. FINDATA) - Combination of the above/multiple authorization required, e.g., REC + specialized national committee (IR)) <p>Conditions (potentially multiple apply, usually in combination with approval above)</p>	<p>Relevance: depends on scope of provisions and applicability; where the further processing is a "one off" to be included in the 1+MG and includes all subsequent use, it's doable. Where this leads to a continuous responsibility (e.g. ask for approval of DPA for each project), this would have a high impact. Track different rule for different applications.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - public interest (significantly) outweighs risks to individual - minimal risk - seeking consent not feasible / impossible / disproportionate effort / likely to render research impossible or seriously impair research - seeking consent was attempted but unsuccessful - appropriate publication of relevant information. - appropriate safeguards in place. - individual has not already withdrawn consent or objected - Obligation to consult a Data Protection Officer - Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) carried out and published (IT, law 196/2003, s. 110 - public interest basis) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This may additionally require prior consultation with data subjects or DPA re: GDPR Art 36) 	
<p>5. Global Data Processing / Transparency: Information requirements beyond GDPR Art. 13</p>	<p><i>This section describes transparency requirements, i.e., obligations to provide certain information about how data are handled to data subjects. General information-giving requirements are described by Articles 13 in the GDPR. These requirements apply equally to primary purposes of processing, as well as to further processing. There are exceptions to these information-giving requirements, however, namely for research purposes under certain conditions such as that the obligation to give information is disproportionate, and other means of publication are pursued (Art 14(5)(b)), and with certain safeguards in place (Art89(1)). Member states may impose additional transparency requirements beyond the GDPR, usually specifically for genetic testing or for participation in health research or genetic/genomic research</i></p> <p><u>Healthcare / genetic testing</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Right to genetic counselling - Potential significance of the results for the patient - Potential significance of the results for the patient’s family or relatives - Possibility to contact family members in case the information is relevance for them - Possibility of false negatives or positives - Right not to know (e.g., secondary/incidental findings from genetic/genomic testing). <p><u>Health, Genetic, or Genomic Research</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Any benefits, risks, and consequences of participating <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Risks and significance of genetic/genomic data for the participant 	<p>Relevance (depends): 1+MG only concerned with information elements about further processing/cross-border access.</p> <p>Solution: transparency best practices and processes as recommendation to address missing information (e.g., re-consent; notification; waiver). Ultimately, correct information is with initial data collector and subsequently with accreditation body which will be acting independently and transparently 1+MG would not take responsibility for this.</p>

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Risks and significance of genetic/genomic data for family members or relatives○ Possibility and significance of incidental findings; individual genetic/genomic findings- Description of specific safeguards in place.<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Measures adopted to allow the identification of data subjects only for the time necessary (IT, Garanti, s 4.11)- Specific information about third party recipients of data/samples<ul style="list-style-type: none">○○ Information on where the biosamples are stored, who has access, how and if they are transferred, analysed and what happens to them afterwards (ES)○ right to withdraw and consequences of withdrawal of consent on data/samples○ what happens if the data/samples are no longer needed, may be other points to consider.- Research-specific information requirements,<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ e.g. derived from ethics requirements such as the possibility to be contacted and for which reasons (e.g. purpose, design, methods applicable in the course of research, foreseeable benefits for data subject, ethics approval, damage compensation, guarantee of confidentiality,○ Sponsors. (LT)○ Voluntary participation. (LT)○ Gratuity. (LT)○ Information on range and number of subjects involved in the research, the duration of the research, and the methods of storing samples or data (HU: in case of population research)- Necessary information to be provided where broad consent is employed- For minors, a requirement to inform a minor when reaching a certain age (e.g., 15/18) that his/her data has been previously collected with permission of the legal guardian	
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<p>6. Data Generation / Data (and Metadata) Quality Requirements.</p>	<p><i>This domain focused on legal standards that clearly impact data quality. We did not, however, find any legal rules that specifically articulate a data quality standard. Rather, we found legal mechanisms or processes that influence standards for data quality. Usually, these mechanisms would influence minimum standards for data quality. Note this section focuses solely on legal requirements that influence standards of data quality and not soft law, voluntary standards (e.g., ISO), or best practices. However soft law may be incorporated by reference (e.g., in establishing a professional standard of care). Another group in the 1+MG is working on quality standards for data inclusion.</i></p> <p>Legal mechanisms that influence data quality standard:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Legally appointed committee (e.g., national data centre) ● Professional duties ● Laboratory regulations/accreditation ● Medical device regulations ● Scientific/Ethics review body requirements 	<p>Relevance: Data generators will follow national/regional data quality standards. In a genome initiative these may be set by a committee defined in the set-up law. Any quality standards enshrined in law is likely to be a minimum standard, meaning they do not preclude voluntary adoption of higher quality standards. Nevertheless, the designing of these minimum standards should carefully take into consideration many parameters such as national legislation.</p> <p>Possible solution: Low quality data could be excluded from 1+MG or tagged with a clear disclaimer.</p>
<p>7. Data Generation / Data formats / ontologies (e.g. SNOMED; ICD-10) / interoperability requirements</p>	<p><i>This domain focuses on types of legal rules that impact data interoperability. Similar to data quality, no specific rules were identified; rather, there may be legal mechanisms or processes that influence data interoperability. These mechanisms are similar to those for data quality (see above).</i></p>	<p>Relevance: Interoperability issues (and lack of harmonized metadata) can affect the scientific/medical value of the resource. It may be possible to retrospectively standardize data through curation for 1+MG, or to encourage voluntary adoption of 1+MG standards.</p>
<p>8. Data Subject Rights</p>	<p><i>This section looks mainly at restrictions (derogations) on data subjects rights imposed by Member State law based on Art 89(2). There are already some general restrictions in the GDPR. For example, the right of access “shall not adversely affect the rights and freedoms of others.” Art 15(4), 17(3)(d)) Any restrictions may only apply where “strictly necessary” and where justified and documented.</i></p>	<p>Derogations from data subjects’ rights may be subject to GDPR or national limitations (e.g., certain applications). They may also be</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - no derogations for scientific research purposes - derogations to any of the arts 15,16,18,21 based on Art. 89 permitted where necessary (right would make research impossible or seriously impair the research). - derogation based on Art. 23 - art 15 derogation if disproportionate effort - derogations subject to conditions (e.g., research plan, responsible person, purpose bind; no third party access, public interest research, DPIA, CoC) - derogation subject to explanation to DPA (BE) - derogations for special category data subject to additional conditions (only with a DPIA or code of conduct) - derogation only for certain institutions or certain purposes (e.g. public interest research) - derogations do not apply where there are legal or direct affects the data subject (DEN) - postponement of rights - Art 17 derogation concerning the results of the research - Art. 17: if erasure would conflict with retention periods set by statute or contract - data subjects' rights applicable also for deceased people (object / prohibit data use after death) or direct relatives (all rights under the GDPR) - limitation of access rights (e.g. not to genealogy; LV) - Art 16 - rectification/completion recorded but underlying data does not have to be modified if they produce no effect on research outcome (IT, law 196/2003, s. 110) 	<p>subject to conditions and safeguards.</p>
<p>9. Storage / Retention period</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specific record keeping period required for primary purpose of collection (e.g., healthcare) - criteria/process related to primary purpose - criteria/process related to further processing prescribed by legislation (e.g., registries) - criteria/process related to further processing, as long as its described in consent (e.g., research) - Periods when data needs to be deleted after withdrawal of consent (HU) - Documentation obligations in healthcare 	<p>Relevance: may affect long-term availability of data from 1+MG and reproducibility. Responsibility and tracking processes needed.</p>

<p>10. Storage / Requirements re: pseudonymisation / de-pseudonymisation</p>	<p><i>Member State requirements that go beyond GDPR principles or apply specific rules to enforce them. Note that art 11 GDPR is generally relevant here, providing derogations from certain data subject rights where data are pseudonymised.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trusted third party (national body) to replace national ID with sector/institution one - Trusted third party required to pseudonymize - Limitations when data can be de-pseudonymised (e.g. only for research and scientific purposes (EE); health of donor, changes in genealogy (LV)). - Designated individual for de-pseudonymised data. - A technical and functional separation between the research team and those who carry out the pseudonymization and keep the information that makes re-identification possible. There is an express commitment to confidentiality and not to carry out any re-identification. Specific security measures are adopted to prevent re-identification and access by unauthorized third parties. (ES) 	<p>Relevance: likely doesn't matter to 1+MG how the pseudonym is generated.</p>
<p>11. Linkage / Requirements when processing national IDs</p>	<p><i>The possibility to use national IDs to uniquely identify a person is relevant where data are collected over different sources and/or over different time points. It limits the likelihood that the same person is entered under multiple pseudonyms (e.g. rare disease patients visiting different hospitals in search of diagnosis; misspelling of names) or that data belonging to different people are linked under the same pseudonym (because of similar names; other parameter used to create a pseudonym).</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Only in the context of certain purposes - Only in the context of certain legal bases - Only in certain circumstances (for important necessities requiring information) - If certain exclusion criteria do not apply - If informed consent is given (e.g. AT for linking - Gentechnikgesetz) - If certain TOMs are fulfilled - No ID exists 	<p>Relevance: may affect data completeness/linkage to associated health data and therefore the quality of information; may affect possibility of followup with provider/subject where a wrong link was created.</p>
<p>12. Hosting / Rules for data repositories / national data centres</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hosting of defined data (e.g. genomic) for defined purposes; general definition of registries for research purposes - Documentation requirements on data access and the corresponding retention time. - Duty of confidentiality 	

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Defined TOMs for data registries- Specific Contractual terms required for data sharing- Requirements on transfer or transmission to third countries (anonymisation, pseudonymisation, approval procedures, limitation to Chapter V safeguards to ensure adequate data protection, HU; only for defined purposes (may or may not include genetic databases; requirement of consent, LV)- Requirements on supervision of databases containing genetic data (PT: where it can identify a family member)	
<p>13. Secondary use / a. Permitted purposes</p>	<p><i>This section covers rules that expressly limit secondary use to certain purposes; this may in particular apply to genomic data or data collected in a certain context (e.g. genomic testing in healthcare). This includes healthcare laws defining categories compatible further processing, laws that set up genome registries etc. Defined purposes included explicitly in legislations for secondary use usually mean that an exemption based on Art. 9(2)i/h/j can be used. However, this usually does not exclude further purposes based on consent.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- public interest research- medical research,- pharmaco-genomic research,- epidemiology,- biomedical research,- biological research- healthcare,- public health,- policy development- quality management (by new controller)	

<p>b. Legal Basis / Legitimation.</p>	<p>Healthcare For healthcare to individuals other than the data subject, this may fall to medical confidentiality rules (e.g., consent or imminent threat to life)</p>	<p>Research: Further Processing: Art 5(1)(b) & Art 89(1) <i>Art. 5(1)(b) together with recital (50) allows research as compatible processing to continue using the original legal basis that data was collected under. Some countries address this in their legislations</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not addressed - Legal basis only available for compatible further processing by the initial controller. - Legal basis can be extended to other controllers for compatible further processing (ES) - Specific safeguards required (eg.pseudonymisation, encryption, DPO etc.) or specific situations (areas related to the initial one) 	
<p>c. Conditions</p>	<p><i>Conditions that apply. Some of these may be repeated in S 4.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explicit consent required (e.g., exception to professional secrecy) - Explicit consent required AND DPA approval (e.g., automated decision making) - Explicit consent required by default. Under other legal bases, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Approval by DPA - specific project (e.g., MT, IT) o Approval by DPA - general (e.g., IT) o Approval by national/institutional REC [or in their absence of DPA] o Approval by DAC o Approval by director or DPO (e.g. HU) o Consult with DPO - Other special technical and/or organisational safeguards required for further processing (Art 5(1)(b) / Art. 89(1) - <i>see s 15 TOMs for details</i>) - Additional consent rules for disclosure of data (deceased, diminished capacity, minors) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Consent of family member needed (genetic data) - Data sharing through dedicated repository / permit authority (DK?) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Defined access body o Data access limitations (secure computing environment) o Defined information provision for application process (including dedicated portal) 		

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Requirements for agreements / contracts to be made (agreement between original controller and new controller (unless specific law enables new controller e.g. BE)- Special information requirements on top of Art. 13/14 [currently we have not identified any]- Requirements on data de-identification (anonymised; re-pseudonymised)- Rules when data subjects can be re-identified / re-contacted- Prohibition on secondary use to treat other patients (e.g. Nordic)- Requirements on who /which entity is going to conduct the secondary use- Requirement of good reputation of data user (NL; Statistics NL)- Requirement for national collaboration (ES; according to Nivel report)- Restrictions on use for crime solving, administrative decisions, insurance, etc. other than healthcare or research- Data sharing requirements (e.g. Art 16(2) PT: free access of the scientific community to data emerging from research on the human genome must be guaranteed)	
d. Rules applying to (third party) data users	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Quality requirements of genome data for healthcare use- Default legal basis/legitimation for processing of health and/or genomic data (for research / healthcare / policy development / quality management)- Different TOMs applying in user's jurisdiction, depending on secondary use.- REC review may or may not be required for secondary use data research (SE)- Research must be carried out by or under the supervision of a researcher who has the necessary scientific competence (SE)- Research limitations: human genome research is permitted only for the purpose of acquiring scientifically justified information that may be utilised for the improvement of the health of the person and the whole of society; research must be scientifically justified (LV)	

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<p>14. Re-Contacting of data subjects</p>	<p>Only according to defined mechanisms / by defined person (DK, Health Act)</p>	
<p>15. Dissemination of Results</p>	<p><i>This section considers the results of both testing in healthcare, and the results of research - both the general results and individual results (e.g., findings that may have individual health relevance to participants). We do not include policy or funding requirements e.g., to publish results open access. We did explore Intellectual Property differences across countries on the assumption these were highly harmonized.</i></p> <p><u>Individual Findings of Clinical Relevance</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Requirements for genetic counselling when returning certain genetic test results (when; by whom)- Obligations to offer individual genetic findings (e.g., of health relevance)- Restriction on reporting certain types of findings in some circumstances (DE)- Right to know (e.g., health information) / Right not to know (e.g., individual genetic findings) e.g., Ask whether or not data subject wants to know the results of the research, including any unexpected news concerning them, if the latter represent a concrete and direct benefit for the interested parties in terms of therapy or prevention or awareness of the reproductive choices. (IT, Garanti, s 4.11)- Restrictions on sale or commercialisation of genetic and/or health data (SL)<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Cost for sharing samples / data: donation, transfer, storage and use of biological samples for both the source subjects and the depositors, must be devoid of any purpose or profit motive. Personal genetic data may not be used for commercial purposes (ES)	

<p>16. TOMs (technical & organisational measures)</p>	<p><i>The source of these legally binding TOMs may be legislation (LUX), general regulation set out by a Ministry (IE) or administrative agency, the DPA (IT), or a specific decision by the DPA. Voluntary codes of conduct are not included unless rendered legally binding by reference. The TOMs may apply variously depending on the type of data (e.g., personal data, health data, genetic data), the purpose (e.g., research), the legal basis, the context (e.g., public v private sector; high-risk processing), and the type of processing (use, transfer, publication of results).</i></p> <p><i>Overall, Member States may take the following approaches to imposed TOMs:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - list of required TOMs (e.g. FINDATA, certain cases DE) - list of TOMs required by default, but possibility to exclude certain TOMs where justified and documented. (LU) - list of recommended TOMs - risk-based and proportionate approach with ongoing evaluation (FI, maybe also DE) - no list - risk-based and proportionate approach with ongoing evaluation (DK;NO) 	
<p>Required level/process of de-identification before processing/transmission/publication of results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pseudonymized or equivalent (ES) - Anonymization, pseudonymisation or other separation measure guaranteeing data “cannot be used to adopt decisions or take actions concerning data subjects” (LU) - Identifiable exceptionally permitted <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o If necessary and overriding public interest + limited adverse effect on DS rights o if necessary and scientific interest outweighs DS rights. - Anonymisation prior to the dissemination of the data/results <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o unless the interest of third parties in such dissemination overrides the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject. 		
<p>Encryption (at rest and in transfer)</p>		
<p>Restriction of access by person and role; individual access approvals (incl. documentation)</p>		
<p>Definitions of responsibilities of employees with respect to data processing (incl. documentation)</p>		
<p>Employees acting on documented instructions/regularly trained</p>		
<p>Requirement to have a DPO</p>		
<p>Certification of data centre /Limitation to a certain processing environment</p>		
<p>Logging of data access (e.g. who; why; processing performed); potentially how long logs need to be kept</p>		
<p>Basic assessment of data privacy risks; Formal Data protection impact assessment (including the publication thereof); data management plan, reidentification risk of pseudonymised or anonymised data (ES)</p>		

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Policies to be in place (and documented; rules for documenting policies) <ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Erasure / sanitisation of files and devices○ Emergencies○ Data breach○ Passwords○ Data classification○ DPIA○ Methods of protection	
Classification of data by its value and degree of confidentiality	
Description of technical resources for processing the data	
Internal / external audits and their frequency	
Research ethics approval	
Requirement of professional secrecy for processing	
Restriction on where data can be stored	
Restriction on duration for which data can be stored	
Authentication and Authorization protocols	
International transfer requires approval by DPA if not using standard safeguards (ES)	

References:

- Johan Hansen, Petra Wilson, Eline Verhoeven, Madelon Kroneman, Mary Kirwan, Robert Verheij, Evert-Ben van Veen, Assessment of the EU Member States’ rules on health data in the light of GDPR (Dec 2020).
- May 2020 Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and Council entitled “Data protection as a pillar of citizens’ empowerment and the EU’s approach to the digital transition - two years of application of the General Data Protection Regulation”
- TIPIK Legal (European Commission): Report on the implementation of specific provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation. (6 January 2021) <https://www.dataguidance.com/sites/default/files/1609930170392.pdf>
- W3C Data Privacy Vocabulary <https://dpcvg.github.io/dpv/#vocab-technical-organisational-measures>